

**Studies in the Coagulation of Colloids from the
Standpoint of Smoluchowski's Theory.
Part IV. Variation of the Surface
Tension during the Coagulation
of the Manganese Dioxide Sol.**

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It was observed in Part II (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 377) and Part III (*ibid.*, 1932, 9, 157) of this series, that in the *slow* coagulation of the arsenious sulphide sol by dilute sulphuric acid, the departure from the requirements of Smoluchowski's theory (as shown by the diminution in β) occurred in all the cases, examined during the initial stages of coagulation. In view of its unexpected character, it was thought desirable to investigate the above conclusion employing a method of measuring coagulation, different from that used previously (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

The manganese dioxide sol was prepared by Cuy's method (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1921, 25, 415; also *cf.* Joshi and Narayan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 883) and stocked in well cleaned silica vessels. The sol contained a small amount of potassium hydroxide which was found to be necessary for its stability. The colloid content of the sol was determined by treating a known volume of the sol with a known volume of standard oxalic acid solution, acidified with dilute sulphuric acid. The progress of the coagulation was followed by measuring the surface tension of the coagulating sol by means of a stalagmometer. The sol was so dilute that its density was found to be practically the same as that of water. The values of the surface tension of the sol, relative to that of water taken as unity, were obtained, therefore, from a knowledge of the significant drop numbers only. Coagulations were also studied when suitable amounts of solutions of sodium oleate and of sugar were added to the sol, before the addition of the coagulator solution. Two principal series of coagulation were studied. In the first, KCl in different concentrations was the coagulator; in the other BaCl_2 was used. In any given series, to a fixed volume of the sol,

varying amount in c. c. of the coagulator solution of a definite concentration and such amounts of water were added so that the volume of the coagulating mixture was always constant. These values for any given coagulation are cited in reference to the corresponding coagulation-time curve in Figs. 1—7. The concentrations of the protector, the coagulator solution, and of the colloid shown in the following results refer to their values before mixing for coagulation. The colloid concentration was 0.87 g. MnO_2 per litre in all these cases (that is, in Figs. 1—3, and 6, 7). Figs. 4 and 5 refer to coagulations by BaCl_2 and KCl respectively of a sol containing 0.695 g. MnO_2 per litre. The mode of getting the β -time curves in Figs. 4—6 and of data in Tables I—V is explained later.

DISCUSSION.

These results show that except when sodium oleate was added (cf. Fig 7, curves 1, 2) the surface tension of the coagulating sol

FIG. 1.

Coagulation by KCl (0.87 g. MnO_2 per litre).

Curve 1—20 c. c. of the sol + 4 c. c. $M/1000\text{-BaCl}_2$.

Curve 2— „ „ + 2 c. c. „ „ + 2 c. c. H_2O .

Curve 3— „ „ + 1 c. c. „ „ + 1 c. c. H_2O .

diminishes continuously during the progress of coagulation (*cf.* Figs. 1—3; curves A, B, in Fig. 4 and curves C, D in Fig. 5). The greater coagulating power of BaCl_2 than KCl is clearly brought out by comparing the curves in Figs. 1 and 2. A comparison of curves in Figs. 2 and 3 shows that the influence of the addition of sugar is not appreciable on the progress of the coagulation of the sol. In view of the usual (though not invariable) relationship between the adsorbability of a substance and its influence as a coagulant, it is interesting in this case to observe that Bhatnagar, Shrivastav and Gupta (*Kolloid Z.*, 1925, 37, 101) observed that sugar is not adsorbed sensibly by manganese dioxide.

FIG. 2.

Coagulation by BaCl_2 (0.87g. MnO_2 per litre).

Curve 1—	20 c. c. sol + 4 c.c. $M/1000\text{-KCl}$ + 0 c. c. H_2O
Curve 2—	„ „ + 3 „ „ + 1 „ „
Curve 3—	„ „ + 2 „ „ + 2 „ „
Curve 4—	„ „ + 1 „ „ + 3 „ „

FIG. 3.

Coagulation by BaCl_2 in presence of sugar (0.87g. MnO_2 per litre).

Curve 1—20 c.c. sol. + 4 c.c. sugar soln. + 4 c.c. $M/1000 \text{ BaCl}_2$.

Curve 2— „ „ + „ + 2 + 2 c.c. H_2O

Curve 3— „ „ + „ + 1 + 3 „

Sugar soln. (5.5 g. in 100 c. c.)

In the previous papers in this series results are given of the application of Smoluchowski's theory to the coagulations of colloid antimony sulphide (Part I, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 11), and of arsenious sulphide (Part II, *loc. cit.*, Part III, *loc. cit.*). The following equation was used (Part I)

$$\beta = \frac{1}{t} \left[\sqrt{\frac{n_0}{n_t}} - 1 \right] \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

n_0 and n_t denote here the number of primaries at time, $t=0$, and $t=t$, respectively. The quantity n_t , the number of primaries in the system diminishes with the progress of coagulation. It is now assumed that n_t at any given time during coagulation is proportional to the reciprocal of the surface tension of the coagulating sol. The quantity n_0/n_t is thus obtained, and β can therefore be calculated from (i), curves *a*, *b* in Fig. 4, curves *c*, *d* in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 show the variation of β during the various coagulations.

FIG. 4. Coagulation by BaCl₂ (0.695 g. MnO₂ per litre).

Curve A—20 c.c. sol + 4 c.c. N/1000-BaCl₂
 Curve B— " " + 2 " " + 2 c.c. H₂O
 Curves a and b show variation of β during coagulation.

FIG. 5. Coagulation by KCl (0.695g. MnO₂ per litre).

Curve c—20 c. c. sol + 4 c. c. N/1000-KCl
 Curve d— " " + 2 " " + 2 c. c. H₂O
 Curves c₁ and d₁ show variation of β corresponding to c and d.

FIG. 6.

Time variation of β in expts. Figs. 1—3.

Curves are marked and numbered similarly to the corresponding coagulation-time curves in Figs. 1—3.

It is known that in general and contrary to the requirements of Smoluchowski's theory, the constant β diminishes with time in the

region of slow coagulation. Mukherjee and Mazumdar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 785) and others have tested the following equation deduced from Smoluchowski's theory.

$$\Sigma n_t = n_0 / (1 + \beta t) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

where Σn_t denotes the total number of particles at a time during coagulation. It follows from this equation that starting with different samples of a given sol ($n_0 = \text{constant}$) in coagulations due to different coagulators, the relative times t_1/T , t_2/T , t_3/Tetc., corresponding to the same stage of coagulation, will be constant, that is, independent of the actual stage of coagulation, in the different series examined. A stage of coagulation is usually considered to be characterised by the value of some property such as the relative opacity etc., which has been found to vary continuously during the progress of coagulation. The last named and other workers have found that in slow coagulation t_1/T etc., is more constant, and that therefore the above theory is more followed, during the *initial* stages of coagulation than afterwards. This conclusion is contrary to the foregoing results showing the diminution of β during the different series of coagulation, calculated from equation (i). Essentially similar results were obtained previously (*cf.* Parts I—III, *loc. cit.*), the degree of coagulation being determined by a method different from that adopted in this work. It is interesting in this connection to examine Anderson's results on the *slow* coagulation of gold sols (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1924, 19, 623); β was calculated from equation (i). These data show (Anderson does not however so state) that the diminution of β during slow coagulation is similar to what we have observed.

Equations (i) and (ii) being but deductions from the same theory, this contrariety between the two sets of results not noticed hitherto, is anomalous. This might, in a great measure, be due to the assumptions implied in estimating n_t and Σn_t involved in equations (i) and (ii) respectively. It is important to emphasise here that especially in the case of polydisperse colloids, no method is available for measuring the degree of coagulation with the exception perhaps of the ultramicroscopic method. Deduction of the constancy of t_1/T from equation (ii) implies that a property like relative opacity is proportional to Σn_{t_1} or at least is a single valued function of Σn_{t_1} . We have no means of examining the limits of the accuracy of this assumption. Likewise use of equation (i) necessitates some supposi-

tion in respect of n_s . We have assumed in calculating the foregoing results that n is proportional to the reciprocal of the surface tension of the coagulating sol. It might with equal justification be assumed that the last quantity is proportional to Σn_s , since there is no *a priori* criterion in selecting any property as a quantitative index of the state of coagulation of a given sol. It is of interest therefore to

FIG. 7.

Coagulation by KCl in presence of sodium oleate.

examine the data (*cf.* Tables I—V) for t/T calculated on the last assumption, for the foregoing series of coagulations. It is seen from these results that in the majority of cases t/T is comparatively more constant during the early stages of coagulation than afterwards. It follows from these findings, therefore, that no deduction as regards the applicability of Smoluchowski's theory to a given region of coagulation is valid, unless we have more quantitative knowledge of the property used for following coagulation, as a function of n_i and Σn_i . A fuller examination of this point will appear in a later communication.

One of the main difficulties in this work was that coagulation produced but small variation in the property used for following its course, *viz.*, surface tension. This together with the time of observation required in this method rendered the examination difficult especially of the initial stages in enough detail. It was thought therefore to increase the duration of the coagulation by introducing small amounts of a protector like sodium oleate, which would reduce the coagulation rate. It was found, however, that the relation between surface tension and the stage of coagulation is almost completely altered by but small changes in the concentration of the protector. Only three of the coagulation-time curves obtained in the course of these experiments have been given (Fig. 7) which serve to illustrate the effect just mentioned. In this connection it is of interest to mention the work of Anderson (*loc. cit.*) on the *rapid* coagulation of gold sols. Anderson added glycerol (which is a well known protector) to his sol in order to reduce the coagulation rate to a measurable value without changing the type of coagulation. In view of the results now discussed, it is obvious that the use of this artifice can only follow on testing whether the course of coagulation is materially disturbed by the addition of the protector.

TABLE I (*cf.* Fig. 1).

T	...	12'	24'	36'	60'	72'	96'	132'
t_1	...	30'	58'	84'	120'	150'	198'	306'
t_2	...	69'	120'	180'	240'	300'	384'	540'
t_1/T	...	2.5	2.4	2.2	2.0	2.2	2.0	2.3
t_2/T	...	5.7	5.0	5.0	4.0	4.1	4.0	4.0

TABLE II (cf. Fig. 2).

T	...	4'	12'	36'	100'	180'
t_1	...	11'	32'	72'	168'	270'
t_2	...	22'	52'	96'	216'	372'
t_1/T	...	2.6	2.6	2.0	1.68	1.6
t_2/T	...	5.5	4.3	2.7	2.16	2.6

TABLE III (cf. Fig. 3).

T	...	6'	12'	24'	36'	40'	72'	84'
t_1	...	12'	30'	60'	76'	90'	146'	168'
t_2	...	24'	60'	108'	152'	180'	276'	300'
t_1/T	...	2.0	2.5	2.5	2.1	2.25	2.0	2.0
t_2/T	...	4.0	5.0	4.5	4.2	4.5	3.8	3.6

TABLE IV (cf. Fig. 4).

T	...	6'	12'	15'	33'	60'	102'
t_1	...	24'	36'	51'	72'	120'	118'
t_1/T	...	4.0	4.0	3.4	2.1	2.0	1.1

TABLE V (cf. Fig. 5).

T	...	18'	30'	60'	90'	120''	150'
t_1	...	36'	60'	96'	135'	168'	216'
t_1/T	...	2.0	2.0	1.6	1.5	1.4	1.4

T , t_1 , t_2 , etc. are times in minutes read off from curves in the corresponding Figures.